

Popular Article

Case Study of ‘Desi Kadaknath Farms

Chandan Kumar, Anil Kumar Sharma and J Morya
KVK Jhabua (M.P)

Published on: 13.1.2023

Abstract

Being labelled as a ‘Black Meat’ which provides high quality protein with lesser fat and cholesterol compared to its counterparts, Kadaknath can be termed as the most preferred delicacy for the health-conscious people. Earlier, the farming of this bird was done by local farmers of Jhabua with limited amount of training and technology. The output was not commendable with most of the birds perished at a very young age. However, the situation is fast changing now. Owing to concerted efforts undertaken by Gov. in the last few years to save the bird, this breed of black chicken is now fostering well. Mrs. Pushpa Dohare is one of the emerging entrepreneurs in Jhabua who is now famous for Kadaknath.

Introduction

Smt. Pushpa Dohare, W/O Mahaveer Singh Dohare aged 35 years completed primary schooling having 7 acres of lands of land available for farming with 6 acres irrigated by tube well and nearby ponds also. She is having Kadaknath birds and commercial hatchery for chick production for their livelihood and income generation. Participation in a 30 days long Skill based training program organised under *Agriculture Skill Council of India, NSDC, New Delhi* at KVK Jhabua in “Small Poultry Farming” encourage her to take up Kadaknath farming initially later on after gaining experience instilled first private hatchery in Jhabua (M.P) having 5000 Kadaknath chicks/ month. She has 3000 original Kadaknath parent stock which was procured from KVK Jhabua in 2015.

Achievement: -

1. Got appreciation certificate of Hon’ble Collector of Jhabua for Kadaknath based entrepreneurship development 2021
2. Got appreciation certificate from Hon’ble Collector helping under ODOP Program of M.P and fulfil the demand of Kadaknath chicks in 2022.
3. Azolla based feeding; Hydroponics, drumstick leaf feeding is innovative technique she is doing in their farms which makes their product highly valuable.
4. She is getting Net income of Rs. 6,00,000.00 per year.
5. Their farms registered in official website of Gov. of Jhabua (www.kadakanth.co.in)

Importance for farmers: -

The major factors contributing to the success is support and encouragement extended by family and friends. Hands holding provided by various public agencies like State Veterinary Department and KVK Jhabua for technical guidance and Central scheme like NLM for financial support. She is also doing other agricultural activities like crop production, horticulture activities for additional income. She is supporting other woman's also to impart their basic knowledge to them to for their livelihood securities.

DDVS, Jhabua Dr Wilson damor, Dr Chandan Kumar, scientist KVK Jhabua and other officers visited their farm

'Desi Kadaknath Hatchery' of Mrs. Pushpa Dohare at Antarweliya, Jhabua

Crop production activities in their farms

Azolla at Kadaknath Farm

Mrs. Pushpa with their Kadaknath

Fish pond in their IFS Model based farming system

INCOME GENERATION THROUGH DIFFERENT ACTIVITIES: -

Component Description		Period 2020-21			
Components	Names	Area (Acre)/No	Production (Q/Liter/No.)	Gross Income (Rs.)	Net Income (Rs.)
Field crop-1	Soybean,	4 Acre	18q	71100.00	60000.00
Field crop 2	Urd	2 Acre	7q	44100.00	22000.00
Hort. Crop 1	Maize	3 Acre	17q	31790.00	20000.00
Hort. Crop 2	Wheat	3 Acre	26q	50050.00	40000.00
Livestock 1	Cow-2		1250 liter	50000.00	28000.00
Livestock 2	Goat-05		8 kids/year	50925.00	39000.00
Kadaknath hatchery (Desi Kadaknath Farms)	Kadaknath chicks Adult Kadaknath		2000 chicks/month Adult birds-5007	1440000.00	700000.00
Total				1737965.00	909000.00

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